

Application of Refractive Index in the Study of Chemical Constitution. Part III. Another Constant R_p Related to the Constant K_r

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A new physical constant R_p , additive and constitutive at a constant temperature (20°), given by

$$R_p = \frac{P}{n^2 + 2}$$

where P is parachor and n , the refractive index, has been suggested. The atomic, group, and structural values of the constant have been evaluated and it has been applied in the study of structural problems and in mixtures of two components.

In an earlier communication¹, an expression:

$$K_r = \frac{M}{n^2 + 2}$$

was developed and its application discussed there and in some subsequent communications². The constancy of $1/(n^2 + 2)$ as a characteristic of the substance is confirmed by combining it with the parachor P , thus providing a new function, viz., the parachor-refractivity relation, $R_p = P/(n^2 + 2)$. This function R_p , as K_r , is not independent of temperature, but for a definite wave length and temperature it is additive and constitutive. The wave length and temperature chosen for measurement are for the D-line and 20° respectively (i.e. n_D^{20} , d_4^{20} , γ^{20}). The refractive index and parachor values have been taken mostly from the works of Vogel *et al.*³. From a study of a large number of compounds, the values of the constant R_p have been found to be additive and constitutive. Some of the atomic, structural, and group values have been derived and recorded in Table I.

Like the other constants^{1,4}, K_r and R_r , this new constant R_p has been applied to some problems of chemical constitution and has shown potentialities for further study. A brief account of the applications to structural study and in straight line mixture law is given below.

Structural Study

Some of the conclusions are noted in Table II in which isomeric groups and compounds show significant difference in their R_p values, as expected, because of the different mode of linking of multivalent atoms.

Accumulation of negative atoms or groups shows some increase in the R_p value of the attached group or atoms. Thus R_p value of two COO groups attached to the same

1. This *Journal*, 1962, 39, 57.

2. *Ibid.*, 1963, 40, 550, 553.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933 to 1948.

4. This *Journal*, 1962, 39, 135.

carbon atom comes to 29.44, whereas $2 \times \text{COO} = 29.32 (2 \times 14.66)$. Similarly for chlorine, the value of two chlorine atoms attached to the same carbon atom is 27.88 and $2 \times \text{Cl} = 27.44 (2 \times 13.72)$; for three chlorine atoms attached to the same carbon atom, R_p value is 42.28 and $3 \times \text{Cl} = 41.16$.

TABLE I

Atom, structure or group.	R_p .	Atom, structure or group.	R_p .
CH_2	9.55	CN (aliphatic)	16.05
C (in CH_3)	-2.89	OH (in aliphatic alcohols)	7.28
H (in CH_3)	0.22	NH_2 (n primary aliphatic amines)	11.00
O (in ethers and acetals)	4.00	NH_2 (in primary aromatic amines)	9.35
CO (in ketones)	9.73	NH (in secondary aliphatic amines)	5.69
CO_2 (in esters)	14.66	NH (in secondary aromatic amines)	3.53
CO_2H	18.02	N (in tertiary aliphatic amines)	-1.45
F (aliphatic)	9.00	N (in tertiary aromatic amines)	-4.06
F (aromatic)	10.06	S (in aliphatic sulphides)	8.25
Cl (aliphatic)	13.72	S_2 (in aromatic sulphides)	7.68
Cl (aromatic)	14.49	S_2 (in aliphatic disulphides)	17.20
Br (aliphatic)	15.42	SH (in aliphatic thiols)	14.70
Br (aromatic)	16.37	SH (in aromatic thiols)	14.89
I (aliphatic)	18.07	SCN (in thiocyanates)	24.80
I (aromatic)	19.73	NCS (in isothiocyanates)	23.83
NO (aliphatic nitroso)	13.45	C. C. double bond	8.78
NO (aromatic nitroso)	14.85	C. C. triple bond*	17.79
ONO (aliphatic nitrite)	19.90	C. C. three-membered ring	6.49
NO_2 (aliphatic nitro)	17.81	C. C. four-membered ring	5.72
NO_2 (aromatic nitro)	18.21	C. C. five-membered ring	3.85
N. NO (in nitrosoamine)	13.03	C. C. six-membered ring	2.57
NO_3	22.89	Methyl group	15.76
SO_3	23.31	Phenyl group	41.63
CO_3	19.30	C_3H_5 (allyl group)	31.14
SO_4	28.70	C_4H_9^i (isobutyl group)	44.25
PO_4	24.70	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{sec}$ (secondary butyl group)	44.59
C_3H_7^i (isopropyl group)	35.19	C_4H_9^t (tertiary butyl group)	44.91

*Triple bond in dialkyl unsaturated compounds comes to 19.38.

TABLE II

	Compound or group.	R_p .	Compound or group.	R_p .
1.	Nitrite	19.90	5. <i>o</i> -Xylene	66.25
	Nitro	17.81		<i>m</i> -Xylene
2.	Thiocyanate	24.80	6. <i>n</i> -Butyl chloride	58.09
	Isothiocyanate	23.83		
3.	Nitrate	22.89	Isobutyl chloride	57.89
	Nitrite	19.90		<i>sec</i> -Butyl chloride
4.	Nitroso	13.45	7. <i>n</i> -Amyl acetate	84.43
	Nitro	17.81		Isoamyl acetate

R_p Values in Mixture Law

The straight line mixture law has been tried in two-component systems and the results obtained have been summarised in Table IIIA in which the $R_p(x)$ value of the solute is given when the solvent is benzene and in Table IIIB are shown the $R_p(x)$ value of the solutes in solvents other than benzene.

TABLE III

S. No.	Solute.	$R_p(x)$ form soln.	$R_p(x)$ calc.
		A. Mixtures in benzene.	
1	<i>p</i> -Dioxane	49.23 (mean)	49.93
2	Aniline	Increased from 47.52 to 50.27	51.66
3	<i>m</i> -Cresol	57.09 (mean)	59.14
4	Benzaldehyde	Increased from 53.03 to 56.95	57.76
5	Bromobenzene	Increased from 47.97 to 57.34	57.99
6	Ethyl acetoacetate	Decreased from 86.33 to 71.32	75.15
7	<i>p</i> -Cresol	58.39 (mean)	59.14
8	<i>o</i> -Cresol	57.32 (mean)	59.14
9	Phenol	Increased from 40.53 to 47.85	49.61
10	2,4-Dichlorophenol	65.07 (mean)	65.16
11	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenol	Increased from 50.26 to 55.74	57.85
12	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	Increased from 53.97 to 55.68	57.85
13	Diphenyl ether	86.16 (mean)	87.33
		B. Mixtures in different solvents.	
14	Aniline in <i>p</i> -dioxane	Increased from 45.72 to 50.79	51.66
15	Nitrobenzene in aniline	Increased from 43.66 to 58.81	59.91
16	Chlorobenzene in nitrobenzene	Increased from 51.22 to 55.87	56.50
17	Chlorobenzene in aniline	56.05 (mean)	56.50

A perusal of the results show that the $R_p(x)$ value from solution is affected due to polarity. Thus the difference in $R_p(x)$ value from solution with $R_p(x)$ calculated is small in the case of solute and solvent being both non-polar or having small polarity. When both solute and solvent are polar, difference in these values become greater, particularly in dilute solutions. The $R_p(x)$ value from solution, however, approaches the calculated value when concentration of the solute is increased. Thus extrapolation would provide values from solution in agreement with the calculated value, except in the case of ethyl acetoacetate in which percentage of tautomeric forms may also be changing, producing complications. It is interesting to note that the $R_p(x)$ value of chlorobenzene from solution in aniline agrees with its calculated value and this can be ascribed to the dipole moment of the groups Cl. (-1.5) and NH₂ (1.5) being equal and opposite in sign according to the data of Williams⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

Among the chemicals used were benzene (b.p. 80.0°), aniline (b.p. 183.5°), benzaldehyde (b. p. 179.0°), and phenol (b.p. 182.0°) and these were B. D. H. AnalaR reagents.

Bromobenzene (b. p. 155.5°), *p*-dioxane (b.p. 101.5°), ethyl acetoacetate (b. p. 180.5°), *p*-cresol (b. p. 202.0°), *o*-cresol (b. p. 191.0°), 2, 4-dichlorophenol (b.p. 209.8°), *p*-chlorophenol (b. p. 216.5°), diphenyl ether (b. p. 258.0°), chlorobenzene (b.p. 132.0°), and nitrobenzene (b. p. 210.0°) were B. D. H. laboratory pure chemicals and were twice distilled in a pyrex apparatus and the middle portions (boiling points of which are given above) were stored in stoppered Jena or pyrex bottles for taking readings. *m*-Cresol (b.p. 210.5°) and *m*-chlorophenol (b.p. 214.0°) were Riedel laboratory pure chemicals of which the middle portions of the distillates were stored for use in a like manner. Standard qualitative tests of the chemicals were made before purification and subsequent use. An Abbe refractometer with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 was used for measuring n_D^{20} ; density (d_4^{20}) was measured by a pycnometer and the surface tension (γ^{20}) was measured with a capillarmeter, using weight up to ± 0.001 g., adopting a method similar as that of Richards *et al.*⁵ with a slight modification. Temperature was maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

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